

THE CONCEPT OF MODELING IN APPLIED MATHEMATICS AND ITS PRACTICAL APPLICATION.

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ANNOTATION

Mathematical models are effective means of answers established by humans to solve real-world problems. Complex wireless communication can establish information interaction between vehicles, in order to reduce the delay time of the coordination control optimization timing scheme in coordination delay time. For smart car driving, a complex signal system, this study first establishes a relevant mathematical model. It is used to compare three mathematical models commonly used today. The results obtained under the same conditions show that the mathematical model is better in dealing with the complex signal system in terms of transmission accuracy in all segments.

Keywords: Modelling examples, Modelling cycle, Modelling competencies, Metacognition, Scaffolding

Introduction. Mathematical modeling is to establish a mathematical model according to actual problems, solve and calculate the mathematical model, and then solve the actual problems in life according to the calculated results. The essence of a mathematical model is a dynamic simulation, not a fixed way of thinking. It is the use of mathematical symbols, mathematical formulas, languages, graphics, etc., to abstract, summarize, and describe the essence of the problem, so as to explain some objective phenomena and development laws in life. Mathematical modeling requires people to flexibly use the relevant knowledge of mathematics, as well as to carefully observe and analyze the real problems in life, abstract from the problems, and extract the mathematical model, which is called mathematical modeling. Since mankind began to tie ropes, mathematics, as the foundation of all disciplines, has developed significantly along with the progress of human technology. Every century of mankind has been the century of mathematics,

and mathematics has emerged and developed throughout the history of human civilization [1]. In this century, mathematics has once again demonstrated its irreplaceable power because of the rapid development of computer technology, which has ushered in digitalization in all industries. Mathematics represents absolute rationality, which removes the pretense of things and represents their essence abstractly yet intuitively. That is why numbers have found deeper and wider application in many fields and joint disciplines such as biomathematics, financial mathematics, and physical mathematics have emerged [2]. And mathematical modeling, as the most useful form in the field of science and social life, has become a necessary way to apply mathematics in the context of big data [3].

Methods and Materials.

In recent years, with the increasingly proficient use of mathematics, mathematical models have penetrated a wide range of industries. Together with the rapid rise of related technologies such as the Internet, deep learning, artificial intelligence, and big data, the application of mathematical models in complex signaling systems has also received increasing attention from the general public and related practitioners [9]. As the most popular means of transportation nowadays, the automobile not only carries the work of human transportation but also is the basis of the modern transportation industry. And the traditional automobile industry introduces new and high technology and carries out technological substitution, and upgrade to become a smart car is a typical complex signal system. The concept of a smart city has been proposed for more than a decade, and nowadays, the intelligent transportation system is one of the first projects to be realized on the ground. And the vehicle wireless communication network has already achieved regional coverage on the city roads and highways of several large cities, which has laid a solid foundation for the popularization of the intelligent transportation network system. The simultaneous development of wireless signal systems and intelligent vehicles has positive implications for enhancing road safety, reducing environmental pollution, improving traffic

efficiency, and reducing manpower waste. The application of mathematical modeling in this complex signal system is very important and irreplaceable, which reflects the practical significance and great economic value of this study.

The contribution of research innovation is that the mathematical model developed in this research has better transmission accuracy in all segments when processing complex signal systems. In this study, a mathematical model is established based on the Doppler effect caused by signal propagation during vehicle operation. With the increase in the number of signal seeds in the system, the signal accuracy of the mathematical model is generally improved, which indicates that the more the number of tree layers generated for the actual transmission of signals, the higher the propagation accuracy. However, the phenomenon of a slight decrease after reaching the critical value may be due to the overflow of tree nodes caused by the excessive depth of the generated tree, resulting in the reduction of signal propagation accuracy. As the information exchange capacity of the mathematical model in this study is enhanced, the congestion during the peak commuting period is greatly reduced. The mathematical model implemented in this section next quantifies the optimization of complex wireless systems and intelligent transportation networks. The results show that the area surrounded by the yellow area is smaller than the area surrounded by the blue line, which means that the timing scheme optimized by the coordination control achieves the expected effect on the coordination delay time control and reduces the average delay time of all intersections in the road network.

Discussion and Results. Application of Mathematical Modeling in the System.

The mathematical model developed in this study has a high recall value and will have a strong predictive power when calculated using positive class samples, which can be used in complex wireless signal systems for smart cars. To verify the signal transmission accuracy of the mathematical model developed in the previous section, it is used to compare with three mathematical models commonly used in traffic systems today. These three models are the BinOCT model, CART model,

and C4.5 model, and the results obtained from the tests conducted under the same conditions are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Comparison of signal transmission accuracy with three common mathematical models.

A comparison with three commonly used mathematical models shows that the mathematical model established in this study has a better transmission accuracy in all segments in dealing with complex signal systems. When the number of signal leaf nodes is in the interval of 25 to 30, the signal transmission accuracy is even the highest at 75.6%. This indicates that the use of branch boundary constraints reduces the search space and also achieves high classification prediction accuracy. In the interval 0 to 10, where the number of signal leaf nodes is small, the mathematical model developed in this study also shows good accuracy. This indicates that the model has good performance in maintaining sparsity without weakening its signal transmission accuracy.

This experiment next selects the variation of the accuracy of the mathematical model with the number of signals in the three signal patterns for different values of the number of random signals in the smart car communication system. The obtained results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2

A line graph of the accuracy of the mathematical model in three signal modes as a function of the number of signals.

The overall increase in signal accuracy of the mathematical model for the three signal modes with the number of seeds of the system signal indicates that the more layers of the tree generated for the actual transmission of the signal, the higher the accuracy of the propagation. However, the phenomenon decreases slightly after reaching a critical value. This may be because too much tree depth will generate overflow tree nodes, resulting in a decrease in signal propagation accuracy. Therefore, the maximum tree depth is the optimal solution for the three signal propagation modes. Then observing one by one, it can be found that the vehicle-to-vehicle signal transmission mode V2V has the highest accuracy, and the accuracy increases as the number increases. This is due to the fact that the mathematical model in this study focuses on eliminating the Doppler Effect caused by signal transmission between vehicles. The V2P mode between vehicles and pedestrians or cyclists and the V2N mode between vehicles and the central network, although the signal transmission accuracy is lower than V2V, reach a minimum of more than 85% at a signal leaf number of 11, which can fully meet the demand in practical use. The above test results show that the mathematical model established in this study can propagate signals more accurately in the case of all three signal modes, which is scientific and reliable.

A number of vehicles in different states of the traffic system are selected, and the relevant data are collected to draw ROC curves using a mathematical model. The three main modes of vehicles on the road are selected: waiting state, free driving state, and slow driving state. Therefore, the aggressiveness of vehicles and the vulnerability of roads will be analyzed as indicators also in the field of transportation. In this study, the ROC curve and confusion matrix are used to characterize these two measures, respectively, and the results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

ROC curves and confusion matrix plots for three vehicle modes.

The four ROC curves in Figure 3(a) reflect the degree of damage caused by the attack of the vehicles on the road in different states and also the load they impose on the complex wireless signal system that assumes the role of scheduling and communication in traffic in different states. It can be seen that the freer and more complex the movement behavior of the vehicle, the greater the load it causes to the road and the system. The initial increments in all three states are rapid and have a large slope, and this trend slows down considerably when a certain point is reached. The possible reasons for this are that the mathematical model developed for this study requires a large amount of kinetic energy to process the initial signal data, but once the system is operating smoothly, the signal data can be collected, analyzed, and transmitted in a stable manner. The results of the confusion matrix show that the rational use of the mathematical model, proper guidance and

scheduling of vehicles, and keeping the vehicles informed of their surroundings can effectively reduce the pressure on the road and the signal system.

The mathematical model also allows for scheduling optimization of traffic flows during peak traffic periods. From the collected data hierarchy strategy, it is clear that the parameters to be iterated are the peak traffic period, peak traffic section, and announcement traffic distribution. Therefore, the existing registered vehicles are first processed in the model according to the splitting strategy to aggregate them. Then, using the feature that the number of vehicles passing the target road section in one day and night must be nonconsecutive positive integers, the interval time of vehicles is used as a reference to achieve loss-free iteration using the mathematical model. Taking the smooth operation of public transportation as the starting target, the target value is gradually optimized through layer-by-layer drawing, and finally, the regional road section passing capacity is effectively converged. Based on the improved mathematical model, to calculate the road throughput capacity of the iterative data map is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4

Calculation of vehicle passing ability data map of regional road sections based on improved mathematical model.

After using the improved mathematical model to optimize the traffic flow of a road section, the throughput capacity of the road section for vehicles is significantly improved. And thanks to the enhanced information exchange between vehicles, between vehicles and pedestrians or cyclists, and between vehicles and

the core network by the mathematical model in this study, the congestion during the peak commuting period is also greatly reduced.

The mathematical model conducted in this section next quantifies the optimization of complex wireless systems and intelligent transportation networks in the assessment. The use of radar plots enables a more detailed demonstration of the computational performance of the mathematical model established in this study in multiple dimensions. In this paper, the vehicle delay times at each intersection are selected as the raw data, and the resultant plots obtained after processing are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5

Mathematical model for congested road traffic optimization before and after the extension time radar map.

In Figure 5, a total of six main roads correspond to six intersections with signalized groups in the target road network. They are arranged in a clockwise manner, and the average delay time of intersections without coordinated control optimization is enclosed by a blue straight line, while the average delay time of intersections after coordinated optimization is enclosed by a yellow straight line. The area enclosed by the blue straight line in Figure 5, i.e., the result of the data without optimization, has sharper edges, with the data at dimensions I18 and T16 being the most distant from the center point and the data at I13 being the closest to the origin. The graph formed by the area enclosed by the yellow lines is relatively rounded, mainly thanks to the data at I13 being enlarged, while the data at dimensions I19, T16, and I18 are significantly reduced. It is also obvious that the

area enclosed by the yellow area is smaller than the area enclosed by the blue line, which means that the coordinated control optimized timing scheme achieves the desired effect in coordinating the delay control and also reduces the average delay of all intersections in the network.

Conclusion. All of the above pitfalls (which is by no means an exhaustive list) can be amended if the team reflects on the quality of their work. If an assumption seemed way off base, students can honestly report out the identified weaknesses of their approach and point the way towards improvements even if they do not have the means or access the information to do so. Even better, a sensitivity analysis can help a student assess the robustness of their model and make comments on its applicability. Much of this circles back to time management.

With more experience modeling, students will naturally gain skills and confidence that can alleviate these issues.

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